

Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)

ISSN (E): 2305-9249 ISSN (P): 2305-9494

Publisher: Centre of Excellence for Scientific & Research Journalism, COES&RJ LLC

Online Publication Date: 1st January 2020

Online Issue: Volume 9, Number 1, January 2020

<https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2020.9.1.1.20>

The Relationship between Organizational Changes and Job Satisfaction in the Jordanian Telecommunication Industry

Najda Hayajneh

Department of Business Management, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan,
n.hayajneh@ju.edu.jo

Taghrid Suifan

Department of Business Management, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan,
t.suifan@ju.edu.jo

Bader Yousef Obeidat

Faculty of Business and Law, The British University in Dubai, Department of
Business Management, The University of Jordan (Unpaid Leave),
b.obeidat@ju.edu.jo

Mohammd Abuhashesh

E-Marketing and Social Media Department, Princess Sumaya University for
Technology (PSUT), Amman, Jordan, m.abuhashesh@psut.edu.jo

Raed Kareem Kanaan

Amman Arab University, Jordan, rk@aau.edu.jo

Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to investigate the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction in telecommunication companies in Jordan. A convenience sample was selected from among employees working at three communication companies (3636 employees) in Jordan. The findings indicate a significant positive relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction. To increase employees' job satisfaction, their level of job stress during organization change operations in telecommunication companies must be decreased.

Keywords:

Organizational Change, Job Satisfaction, Telecommunication Industry, Jordan

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Citation:

Hayajneh, Najda; Suifan, Taghrid; Obeidat, Bader Yousef; Abuhashesh, Mohammd; Kanaan, Raed Kareem (2020); The Relationship between Organizational Changes and Job Satisfaction in the Jordanian Telecommunication Industry; Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS), Vol.9, No.1, pp:1-20; <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2020.9.1.1.20>.

1. Introduction

Recently, in the dynamic business cycle and competitive environment, organizations have begun searching for new opportunities to achieve a competitive advantage in order to maintain sustainability in the worldwide market. Job satisfaction has become a key component of successful organizations (Abuhashesh, et al., 2019a). Job satisfaction has been studied widely in previous literature and several specialists, managers, and researchers believe that it plays a vital role in employee productivity and retention rate. Job satisfaction can be affected by many factors, such as promotion, wages, benefits, working conditions, leadership, social relationships, and the work itself (Parvin & Kabir, 2011). Currently, organizations must change constantly because development and growth occur through changes (Karajeh & Maqableh, 2014; Maqableh, et al., 2015; Petrou, et al., 2018). Moreover, it is important to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of organizations (Broni, 2017; Caves, 2018). Studies have shown that an understanding of employees' psychological template can affect organizational change (Shah, et al., 2017). The psychology of employees is an important subject to investigate during organizational change. Change can sometimes threaten employees, as it leads to modification of positions and tasks (Oreg, 2006). Employees react passively, aggressively, or honestly during organizational change (Castillo, Fernandez, & Sallan, 2018). Nevertheless, successful organizational change requires employee engagement and involvement (Petrou et al., 2018; Van den Heuvel, et al., 2010). Such changes require the efforts of managers in order to promote positive employee behavior for achieving the organization's goals and objectives (Al-Dmour, et al., 2015; Petrou, et al., 2017). Organizations require leadership and self-motivation of decision-makers in order to utilize talented employees and assess their skills through continuous training and education programs during the change process (Caves, 2018). Organizational change is needed frequently in organizations to update technology and deal with the demands of the competitive market (Shah et al., 2017).

Accordingly, this paper investigates the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction in telecommunication companies in Jordan.

2. Literature Review

This study summarizes the relevant literature and examines the relationship between the organizational change and job satisfaction, with the purpose of developing a theoretical framework and hypothesis for the research:

2.1 Organizational Change

The main purpose of organizational changes is to improve the mission and vision in order to adapt to global changes (Castillo et al., 2018). Organizations struggle to develop and apply different kinds of changes to respond to the rapid developments of the external environment (caused due to technological, social, economic, and political forces). Thus, organizations must react effectively to these challenges and take advantage of the opportunities (Masa'deh, 2012; Masa'deh, et al., 2015; Heckelman, 2017). Organizational change is also related to high expectations of improving performance (Schneider, et al., 1996). Changes come in different forms; whereas some changes impact the organization as a whole, others only affect certain departments, teams, or processes (Yousef, 2017). Both expected and unexpected pressures (external or internal) can force organizations to take corrective measures, such as restructuring, strategies, policies, culture, or approaches, to support organization sustainability and attain competitive advantage (Shah et al., 2017). Successful organizational change requires the acceptance of employees (Fairbrother & Warn, 2003). Employees' attitudes are influenced by understanding the changing conditions as well as the level of impact on them (Cullen et al., 2014).

Most employees do not have enough experience and motivation to feel satisfied with organizational change, which is a reason for resistance to change. Organizations must develop effective change strategies (Bateh, et al., 2013). Researchers agree that communication is the most effective strategy to enhance employee acceptance, which is necessary as employees play a critical role in organizational change (Petrou et al., 2018). The quality of communication during organizational change depends on an organization's ability to provide timely, useful, and relevant information (Petrou et al., 2018; Wanberg & Banas, 2000). The changes are more effective when the three levels within an organization (i.e., individual, group, and organizational) work together (Heckelman, 2017). In most cases, the failure of an organization in adopting a new strategy to deal with the internal and external challenging environments is blamed on the cumulative history of the organization, and this problem must be dealt with (Oliver, 1997). The newly created structures must support the new strategies; however, structures do not change immediately or easily, and require trainings, budgets, transparency performance criteria, performance measures, a culture of engagement, creativity, and incentives (Weil, 2018). New structures usually lead to employee resistance to change and job stress (Ernst Kossek, et al., 2010).

Organizational change comprises a series of efforts to change the structure, goals, technology, and processes of the organization (Yousef, 2017; Yousef, 2000; Carnall, 1986). It is defined as the search for new opportunities for improvement in order to achieve an effective change within an organization (Brown, et al., 2016). Organizational change has also been defined as a new method of operating the organization (Pardo-del-Val, et al., 2012). Golembiewski (1995) defines organizational change as a process of transition between the current situation and the future targeted situation. It is also a normal daily process of working life, in the form of processes such as mergers, relocations, and salary freezes (Castillo, et al., 2018).

Due to these varying definitions, organizational change has been measured using different dimensions. Shinet al. (2012) measured organizational change by three dimensions, these are: behavioral resistance to change, behavioral support for change, and creative behavior for change. However, Dahl (2011) used the following six dimensions to measure organizational change: enhanced skills/knowledge, increased effectiveness, adaptation to turbulent environments, and increased cooperation and coordination within the organization. In this paper , the variables of organizational change were measured using the process of change, readiness for change, and climate of change dimensions, which have previously been used by Khan et al. (2018); Claiborne et al., (2013); Bouckenooghe (2012); and Bouckenooghe et al.,(2009). These dimensions have been widely utilized and found to be valid and reliable for human research (Khan et al., 2018; Claiborne et al., 2013). Moreover, they have been proven to be theoretically and empirically sound in terms of the shortcomings found in the dimensions used in other studies (Bouckenooghe et al., 2009). The first dimension used in this study is the process of change, which is defined by Claiborne et al. (2013) as “the steps taken to implement the change.” This dimension is comprising how a particular change is handled in a project, and is mainly linked to readiness for change (Holt, et al., 2007). It has also been defined as the reactions to organizational change (Khan et al., 2018). Leadership is significantly related to the process of change dimension due to its role of providing rewards and efficiently communicating with employees (Khan et al., 2018). According to Bouckenooghe et al. (2009), process of change is related to four elements: the quality of change communication, participation, attitudes of top management toward the change, and support of supervisors. The second dimension is readiness for change, which implies readiness in terms of the expressions of employees’ physical, psychological, and emotional abilities to perform their job roles (Almomani, 2018). Change readiness is defined as the "gauge of how prepared and able organizational members are for change initiatives" (Appelbaum, 2018).

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

Organizational readiness for change is a new concept, which is defined as the extent to which employees will continue to evolve and engage in the change, such as through participation and support (Von et al., 2018). According to Claiborne et al. (2013), the more readiness for change an organization demonstrates with respect to external environmental pressures, size of the organization, leadership commitments, financial resources, worker attributes, and community attitude toward change, the more there are positive outcomes, such as decreased job stress, increased job satisfaction, and less resistance to change and conflict. Readiness for change requires considerable resources and motivations (Kelly et al., , 2018). According to Von et al. (2018), the readiness for change is measured using four dimensions: personal valence (i.e., employees' belief that the change will be personally beneficial), managerial support (i.e., employees' perception that managers are supportive of the change), appropriateness (i.e., employees' perception that the change is appropriate for the organization) and self-efficacy (i.e., employees' perception that they possess the skills and competencies to successfully cope with change). Values and beliefs are the framework of an organization's culture (Schneider et al., 1996). An understanding of change readiness helps make the right choices regarding the planning, strategies, and tactics required to enhance employee enthusiasm for change (Shah et al., 2017). Effective readiness for change is an immense challenge because of the large human involvement (Broni, 2017).

The last dimension is the climate of change, which has been defined by Tierney (1999) as employees' expectation to be supported and rewarded by the organization during change. It is a global problem that needs cooperation (Field et al., 2014). Climate of change comprises three elements: trust in leadership, politicking, and cohesion (Bouckennooghe et al., 2009). According to Von et al. (2018), it comprises eight dimensions, namely, support, recognition, autonomy, work pressure, fairness, trust, innovation, and cohesion. Hatjidis and Parker (2018) reported that a strong climate for change leads to more opportunities for participation and lower levels of resistance to change. The adoption of change depends on the variables of the organizational climate (Von et al., 2018).

2.2 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is considered an interesting topic to study from organizations' as well as researchers' viewpoints (Parvin & Kabir, 2011; Obeidat, et al., 2017). It was first investigated and highlighted by researchers in 1918 (Suifan & Abdallah, 2017; Abuhashesh et al., 2019b). According to -Nkrumah and Atinga (2013), job satisfaction affects employees' behavior and work outcomes. The work of several researchers has indicated that job satisfaction has a massive effect on attitudes and work outcomes of employees (Suifan, et al., 2017). Previous researchers have agreed that employee satisfaction is one of the most important factors for employees' productivity and loyalty (Amin et al., 2017). Satisfied and positive

employees result in customer satisfaction, which ultimately leads to high financial performance (Sarraf, 2018). Although researchers have proposed several definitions and ideas for job satisfaction, they have not been able to agree on a single definition because of the various complex factors affecting it (Abdallah et al., 2016). Job satisfaction and dissatisfaction were defined by Locke (1969) as "a function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from one's job and what one perceives it as offering or entailing". According to Ahmad et al. (2018), job satisfaction is a measure of the degree to which the employees have a positive or negative feeling toward the internal or external aspects of their jobs. Job satisfaction is a combination of evaluative emotions that employees feel regarding the work environment (Sarraf, 2018). Al-Tit and Suifan (2015) reported that job satisfaction is the level of employees' happiness with their job. Schermerhorn et al. (2012) defined job satisfaction as the "attitude reflecting a person's feelings toward his or her job or job setting at particular point in time." According to Spector (1997), job satisfaction is the feeling that determines whether to remain in an organization or seek another job.

Measuring job satisfaction is a constant challenge for both researchers and managers (Masa'deh, 2016; Hajir et al., 2015). Haque et al. (2012) classified job satisfaction into the dimensions of personal factors and organizational factors. The first dimension includes religion, gender, age, and race, whereas organizational factors include leadership, organizational change, and technology innovation. Al-Abdullat and Dababneh (2018) measured job satisfaction through several dimensions: overall life satisfaction, self-esteem, stress, physical and mental illness, productivity and performance, absenteeism, turnover, and even counterproductive behavior. Lu et al. (2017) measured job satisfaction using four dimensions: superiors, promotion, current job, and remuneration. Yousef (2017) measured job satisfaction using six dimensions (job security, coworkers, promotion, working conditions, pay, and supervision). Job satisfaction was examined by Hayes et al. (2015) using the following six dimensions (pay, autonomy, task requirements, organizational policies, interaction, and professional status). Claiborne et al. (2013) was measured job satisfaction by using dimensions (promotional opportunities, supervision, pay, fringe benefit, communication, nature of work, co-workers, operating procedures, rewards, and overall satisfaction). Herzberg (1966) considered intrinsic job satisfaction as motivating factor. The existence of these factors results in satisfied employees (Baylor, 2010). Intrinsic job satisfaction refers to employees' feelings toward the nature of the job tasks, for example, achievement and control, success, ability to develop skills, and sense of autonomy (Tsounis & Sarafis, 2018; Abdallah et al., 2016). Intrinsic motivation appears from within the employees, and is described as the willingness to do more in order to fulfill tasks (Almomani, 2018). According

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

to Chung and Kowalski (2012), intrinsic factors are related to the job itself, such as personal activities, attitudes toward change, moral values, authority, responsibility, personal feelings of freedom and independence, personal social status, creativity, recognition, and success abilities (Tarcán, 2017). The second dimension is extrinsic job satisfaction. According to Herzberg (1966), the existence of extrinsic job satisfaction factors (or hygiene factors), may not necessarily mean that employees are satisfied; however, their absence might be dissatisfying for employees (Baylor, 2010). Extrinsic job satisfaction refers to employees' feelings toward various aspects of the work situation that are not related to the work itself; for example, quality of the job environment, promotion opportunities, relationships with colleagues, and salary (Tsounis & Sarafis, 2018). According to Abdallah et al. (2016), these factors are related to employees' feelings regarding the job conditions and situations. Furthermore, Masa'deh (2016) stated that these factors are related to aspects of the job environment, such as working conditions, coworkers, and pay. Extrinsic job satisfaction includes elements related to insurance coverage, company policies and practices, opportunities for occupational progression, wages, human relations and leadership/management techniques, colleagues, and working conditions (Tarcán, 2017).

2.3 Organizational Change and Job Satisfaction

Previous research has reported that job satisfaction has an impact on organizational change, and plays an important role in the acceptance of organizational change, as satisfied employees are more likely to willingly accept the change (Yousef, 2017; Yousef, 2000; Abuhashesh, et al., 2019 c). Haque et al. (2012) indicated that employees respond positively to organizational change by enhancing their satisfaction and enthusiasm for work, and providing good services. However, according to Castillo et al. (2018), managers sometimes fail to consider the impact of organizational change on employee satisfaction, morale, and productivity, in the form of desertion, absenteeism, and resistance to change. Lack of trust, self-interest, a difference in the assessment of misunderstandings, and low tolerance for change are the main reasons for resistance to organizational change (Castillo et al., 2018). Hatjidis and Parker (2018) studied the influences of job satisfaction and commitment on the association between relationship quality and an individual's behavioral intention toward organizational change in the hospitality industry. They found that the relationship quality has a positive association with an individual's behavioral intention toward change; in addition, organizational commitment and job satisfaction play a mediating role in the relationship between relationship quality and behavioral intentions toward change. Shah et al. (2017) studied the effects of organizational loyalty, salary, job promotion, and organizational identity on job satisfaction, while suggesting and mediating employee readiness for organizational change; they identified these intrinsic and extrinsic factors that

enable organizational change. Yousef (2017) studied the relationships between job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and attitudes toward organizational change in the local government, and found that employees are highly satisfied with supervisors and coworkers, and only a little satisfied with work conditions and job security; however, they had lower satisfaction with pay and promotion (Aldaas, et al., 2019). Adigwe and Oriola (2015) studied the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction, and found that organizational change affects job satisfaction, but the satisfaction levels of employees depend on the effectiveness of organizational change. Cullen et al. (2014) investigated employees' adaptability and perceptions of organizational change-related uncertainty, and the mediating role of perceived organizational support as an explanation for employees' job satisfaction and performance. Their findings reveal that perceived organizational support explains the impact of perceived organizational change-related uncertainty and individual differences in adaptability on job satisfaction. Claiborne et al. (2013) investigated the role of climate and job satisfaction in employees' perception of readiness for change. According to their findings, not all climates or satisfaction factors are recognized equally while supporting change. Schouteten and Vleuten (2013) investigated the impact of organizational change on job satisfaction in a Dutch voluntary association employing paid and voluntary workers; their findings revealed that organizational changes have a negative impact on voluntary and paid employees' job satisfaction. Judge et al. (1999) examined the managerial responses to organizational change, and found that organizational change was related to extrinsic (job performance, salary, plateauing, job stress level) and intrinsic (job satisfaction, organizational commitment) factors.

On the basis of previous studies, this research developed the following hypotheses:

H01: There is no statistically significant impact of organizational change on job satisfaction.

3. Research Methodology

The methodology of the research, including the research model, is described along with the hypotheses. Furthermore, it presents the research data, including the research population and sample, as well as data analysis. The research model was built on the basis of a previous literature review and is presented in organizational change as the independent variable and job satisfaction is the dependent variable. The participants in this research were taken from three telecommunication companies in Jordan (Zain, Orange, Umnieh). A convenience sample was selected from among the employees. The total number of employees working at these companies has crossed 3,636. The represented sample size includes 348 employees of telecommunication companies in Jordan.

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

To this end, 500 questionnaires were distributed and 442 were returned. Of these, 20 were considered invalid and disregarded; the data of the remaining 422 questionnaires was used, with a response rate of 84%.

3.1 Hypotheses Testing

The purpose of testing the hypotheses is to assess the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis; when the significance level (p-value) is below 0.05, the null hypothesis (H₀) will be rejected and the alternative (H₁) will be accepted, which indicates a positive impact. On the other hand, the null hypothesis is accepted when the p-value is higher than 0.05 (Sekaran & Bogie, 2016). Simple linear regression was used to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

The Pearson correlation estimates the linear relationship between two variables (Thirumalai, et al., 2017). The values of the Pearson correlation coefficient, r , range from +1 to -1. A value higher than 0 indicates a positive relationship (the value of one variable increases, while the other value also increases). A value below 0 indicates a negative relationship (the value of one variable increases, while the other decreases). To test the research hypotheses, the approach proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) was applied. This approach consists of four steps. In the first step, the independent variable (organizational change) was regressed to the dependent variable (job satisfaction) and beta coefficient (0.465***), which was positive and significant; therefore, hypothesis H₀₁ was rejected.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

This research investigates the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction in telecommunication companies in Jordan. It is hypothesized that organizational change impacts job satisfaction. The findings demonstrate the rejection of the hypotheses.

The first finding showed that 21.6% of the variation in organizational change accounted for job satisfaction; the result indicates a significant and positive relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction. Studies have shown that some organizational change factors have a positive impact on job satisfaction, while others have a negative impact (Yousef, 2017; Shah, et al., 2017). The level of satisfaction of employees depends on the effectiveness of change in the organization (Adigwe & Oriola, 2015).

Telecommunication companies have grown to become one of largest and leading businesses in Jordan (Al-Weshah, et al., 2018; Abuhashesh, et al., 2019d). Organizations have begun providing comfortable and appropriate work environments that decrease employees' negative emotions and increase their

job satisfaction levels, in order to improve their performances, especially during organizational change processes (Brewer, et al., 2003; DeTienne, et al., 2012; Eslami & Gharakhani, 2012; Lee & Chelladurai, 2018; Sarraf, 2018). The managements must take into consideration employees' emotional readiness for change by improving the quality of the change processes, such as through support, participation, and communication (before, during, and after the change process), in addition to taking the necessary feedback for continuous improvement and corrective actions (Claiborne, et al., 2013; Abualoush, et al., 2018a,b). Furthermore, the management must enhance the climate of change by improving the trust in leadership, fairness among employees, give incentives, and make efficient use of the resources available (Bouckenoghe, et al., 2009; Parvin & Kabir, 2011; Al-Syaidh, et al., 2016; Al-dalahmeh, et al., 2018; Caves, 2018).

4.1 Practical Implications

One of the most important factors that lead to the success of organizational change is the human resources. Satisfied employees who are treated well are a great asset for the success of an organization. Telecommunication companies face numerous challenges in both internal and external environments; one of the most important internal challenges is to improve job satisfaction and reduce the stress of employees, which leads to improved performance of the organization.

From the findings of this research, managers and leaders can develop several ideas for promoting job satisfaction in telecommunication companies, and guiding companies to improve organizational change, by focusing on the quality of leadership support and communication, understanding employees' needs during change along with their expectations and involvement, which enhances job satisfaction.

Telecommunication is one of the most rapidly growing and highly competitive sectors. Thus, it is possible that telecommunication company employees feel that adopting continuous organizational change strategy is necessary to ensure sustainability in the market, and avoid the risk of losing their jobs. Previous research suggests that any change is stressful, and stress decreases satisfaction; therefore, organizations must provide more attention to stress factors while employing all dimensions of stress in the workplace and work on reducing the negative effects of stress on job satisfaction during organizational change. This can be done by providing a comfortable environment, supporting employee creativity and innovation, training, enhancing interaction between the leadership and staff, and expanding the involvement and contribution of employees. Organizations must spread the culture of quality among employees in order to

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

develop their efficiency. This will ultimately reflect positively on the performance of the organization.

4.2 Limitations

First, the use of convenience sampling and studying only employees of the telecommunications sector in Jordan limits the generalizability of the results. Second, there seemed to be hesitation and resistance from companies to respond and collaborate by sharing their data. Additionally, a set of questionnaires returned by employees were excluded because of their lack of appropriateness.

4.3 Recommendations for Future Research

The present study's findings indicate a significant positive relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction. In addition, telecommunication companies in Jordan should focus on reducing employees' job stress during organizational change in order to raise their job satisfaction. Also, companies should explain the reason behind changes in order to gain high acceptance rates among employees.

The main contribution of this research is in examining the relationship between organizational change and job satisfaction. This research recommends other researchers to investigate the impact of organizational change on job satisfaction using different dimensions and sectors, which helps in determining strategies to improve employees' job satisfaction.

References

- Abdallah, A.B., Obeidat, B.Y., Aqqad, N.O., Al Janini, M., & Dahiyat, S. (2016). An integrated model of job involvement, job satisfaction and organizational commitment: A structural analysis in Jordan's banking sector. *Communications and Network*, 9(01), 28-53.
- Abekah-Nkrumah, G., & Ayimbillah Atinga, R. (2013). Exploring the link between organizational justice and job satisfaction and performance in Ghanaian hospitals: Do demographic factors play a mediating role? *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, 6(3), 189-204.
- Abualoush, S., Bataineh, K., & Alrowwad, A. (2018a). The role of knowledge management process and intellectual capital as intermediary variables between knowledge management infrastructure and organization performance. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Information, Knowledge, and Management*, 13, 279-309.
- Abualoush, S., Obeidat, A., & Tarhini, A. (2018b). The role of employees' empowerment as an intermediary variable between knowledge management

and information systems on employees' performance. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 48(2), 217-237.

Abuhashesh, M., Al-Dmour, R., & Masa'deh, R. (2019a). Factors that affect employees job satisfaction and performance to increase customers' satisfactions. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 1-23.

Abuhashesh, M., Al-Dmour, R., & Masa'deh, R. (2019b). Factors that impact job satisfaction and performance among employees in the Jordanian industrial sector. *Proceedings of the 32nd International Business Information Management Association Conference, IBIMA 2018-Vision 2020: Sustainable Economic Development and Application of Innovation Management from Regional expansion to Global Growth*, 4285-4305.

Abuhashesh, M., Al-Khasawneh, M., & Al-Dmour, R. (2019c). The impact of Facebook on Jordanian consumers' decision process in the hotel selection. *IBIMA Business Review*, 1-16.

Abuhashesh, M., Mohammad, S.J., & Al Khasawneh, M. (2019d). The attitude of Jordanian customers towards virtual stores. *Int. J. Islamic Marketing and Branding*, 4(1), 59-75.

Adigwe, I., & Oriola, J. (2015). Towards an understanding of job satisfaction as it correlates with organizational change among personnel in computer-based special libraries in Southwest Nigeria. *The Electronic Library*, 33(4), 773-794.

Ahmad, K.Z., Jasimuddin, S.M., & Kee, W.L. (2018). Organizational climate and job satisfaction: Do employees' personalities matter? *Management Decision*, 56(2), 421-440.

Al-Abdullat, B.M, & Dababneh, A. (2018). The mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between organizational culture and knowledge management in Jordanian banking companies. *Benchmarking: An International Journal* (just-accepted), 00–00.

Aldaas, A., Jamal, M., & Abuhasheesh, M. (2019). Successful implementation of corporate governance mechanisms in banks. *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*, 8(4), 692-710.

Al-dalahmeh, M., Khalaf, R., & Obeidat, B. (2018). The effect of employee engagement on organizational performance via the mediating role of job

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

satisfaction: The case of IT employees in Jordanian banking sector. *Modern Applied Science*, 12(6), 17-43.

Al-Dmour, R., Obeidat, B., & Almajali, D. (2015). The practice of HRIS applications in business organizations in Jordan: An empirical study. 4th Scientific & Research Conference on New Trends in Business, Management and Social Sciences (COES&RJ-TK15/1).

Almomani, R.Z. (2018). Do employee engagement affects job performance: A study of telecommunication companies in Jordan. *Global Journal of Management And Business Research*.

Al-Syaidh, N., Al-Lozi, M., & AlHarrasi, J. (2016). Transformational leadership and its role on the effectiveness of employees' behavior: A theoretical study. *Journal of Business & Management (COES&RJ-JBM)*, 4(1), 14-35.

Al-Tit, A.A. & Suifan, T.S. (2015). The mediating role of job characteristics in the relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 10(9), 215.

Al-Weshah, G.A., Al-Manasrah, E., & Al-Qatawneh, M. (2018). Customer relationship management systems and organizational performance: Quantitative evidence from the Jordanian telecommunication industry. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 1-21.

Amin, M., Aldakhil, A.M., Wu, C., Rezaei, S., & Cobanoglu, C. (2017). The structural relationship between TQM, employee satisfaction, and hotel performance. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(4), 1256–1278.

Appelbaum, S.H., Profka, E., Depta, A.M., & Petrynski, B. (2018). Impact of business model change on organizational success. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 50(2), 41–54.

Baron, R.M., & Kenny, D.A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173.

Bateh, J., Castaneda, M.E., & Farah, J.E. (2013). Employee resistance to organizational change. *International Journal of Management and Information Systems*, 17(2), 113.

Baylor (2010). The influence of intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction factors and affective commitment on the intention to quit for occupations characterized by high voluntary attrition. Doctoral dissertation. Nova Southeastern University. Retrieved from NSUWorks, H. Wayne Huizenga School of Business and Entrepreneurship, 1(10).

Bouckenooghe, D. (2012). The role of organizational politics, contextual resources, and formal communication on change recipients' commitment to change: A multilevel study. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 21(4), 575-602.

Bouckenooghe, D., Devos, G., & Van den Broeck, H. (2009). Organizational change questionnaire—climate of change, processes, and readiness: Development of a new instrument. *The Journal of Psychology*, 143(6), 559-599.

Brewer, E., & McMaha-Landers, J. (2003). The relationship between job stress and job satisfaction of industrial and technical teacher educators. *Journal of Career and Technical Education*, 20(1).

Broni, K.E. (2017). Exploring the views of leadership at Takoradi Technical University on change readiness after their upgrade. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, University of Cape Coast.

Brown, S., Manning, M.R., & Ludema, J.D. (2016). Organization identity: Its role in organization change. In *Research in Organizational Change and Development* (pp. 145–183). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Carnall, C.A. (1986). Toward a theory for the evaluation of organizational change. *Human Relations*, 39(8), 745-766.

Castillo, C., Fernandez, V., & Sallan, J.M. (2018). The six emotional stages of organizational change. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 31(3), 468-493.

Caves, L. (2018). Lifelong learners influencing organizational change. *Studies in Business and Economics*, 13(1), 21–28.

Chung, C.E., & Kowalski, S. (2012). Job stress, mentoring, psychological empowerment, and job satisfaction among nursing faculty. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 51(7), 381-388.

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

Claiborne, N., Auerbach, C., Lawrence, C., & Schudrich, W.Z. (2013). Organizational change: The role of climate and job satisfaction in child welfare workers' perception of readiness for change. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 35(12).

Cullen, K.L., Edwards, B.D., Casper, W.C., & Gue, K.R. (2014). Employees' adaptability and perceptions of change-related uncertainty: Implications for perceived organizational support, job satisfaction, and performance. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 29(2), 269-280.

Dahl, M.S. (2011). Organizational change and employee stress. *Management Science*, 57(2), 240-256.

DeTienne, K.B., Agle, B.R., Phillips, J.C., & Ingerson, M.C. (2012). The impact of moral stress compared to other stressors on employee fatigue, job satisfaction, and turnover: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 110(3), 377-391.

Ernst Kossek, E., Lewis, S., & Hammer, L.B. (2010). Work-life initiatives and organizational change: Overcoming mixed messages to move from the margin to the mainstream. *Human Relations*, 63(1), 3-19.

Eslami, J., & Gharakhani, D. (2012). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *ARPN Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(2), 85-91.

Fairbrother, K., & Warn, J. (2003). Workplace dimensions, stress and job satisfaction. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18(1), 8-21.

Field, C.B., Barros, V.R., Mach, K.J., Mastrandrea, M.D., van Aalst, M., Adger, W.N., ... & Birkmann, J. (2014). Technical summary. In *Climate Change 2014: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Part A: Global and sectoral aspects. Contribution of working group II to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change* (pp. 35–94). Cambridge University Press.

Golembiewski, R.T. (1995). *Managing diversity in organizations*. Tuscaloosa: University of Alabama Press.

Hajir, J., Obeidat, B., & Al-dalahmeh, M. (2015). The role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing innovation at mobile telecommunication companies in Jordan. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 50(3), 313-330.

Haque, M., Karim, A., Muqtadir, A., & Anam, S. (2012). Dimensions of job satisfaction of library professionals: A qualitative exploration. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*, 2(5), 46-62.

Hatjidis, D., & Parker, A. (2018). The role of relationship quality in raising organizational change acceptance: The case of the Greek hotel industry. *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 1-20.

Hayes, B., Douglas, C., & Bonner, A. (2015). Work environment, job satisfaction, stress and burnout among haemodialysis nurses. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 23(5), 588-598.

Heckelman, W. (2017). Five critical principles to guide organizational change. *Practitioner*, 49(4), 14.

Herzberg, F. (1966). *Work and the nature of man*. Cleveland, OH: World Publishing.

Holt, D.T., Armenakis, A., Feild, H.S., & Harris, S.G. (2007). Readiness for organizational change: The systematic development of a scale. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 43, 232-255.

Judge, T.A., Thoresen, C.J., Pucik, V., & Welbourne, T.M. (1999). Managerial coping with organizational change: A dispositional perspective. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 84(1), 107.

Khan, S.N., Busari, A.H., Abdullah, S.M., & Mughal, Y.H. (2018). Followership moderation between the relationship of transactional leadership style and employees reactions towards organizational change. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 17.

Karajeh, H., & Maqableh, M. (2014). Security of cloud computing environment. *Proceedings the 23rd IBIMA Conference on Vision 2020: Sustainable Growth, Economic Development, and Global Competitiveness*, 2202-2215.

Kelly, P., Hegarty, J., Barry, J., Dyer, K.R., & Horgan, A. (2018). The relationship between staff perceptions of organizational readiness to change and client outcomes in substance misuse treatment programmes: A systematic review. *Journal of Substance Use*, 23(3), 223-239.

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

Lee, Y.H., & Chelladurai, P. (2018). Emotional intelligence, emotional labor, coach burnout, job satisfaction, and turnover intention in sport leadership. *European Sport Management Quarterly*, 18(4), 393-412.

Locke, E.A. (1969). What is job satisfaction? *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 4(4), 309-336.

Lu, Y., Hu, X.M., Huang, X.L., Zhuang, X.D., Guo, P., Feng, L.F., ... & Hao, Y.T. (2017). The relationship between job satisfaction, work stress, work-family conflict, and turnover intention among physicians in Guangdong, China: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*, 7(5), 014894.

Maqableh, M., Rajab, L., Quteshat, W., & Khatib, T. (2015). The impact of social media networks websites usage on students' academic performance. *Communications and Network*, 7(4), 159-171.

Masa'deh, R. (2012). The impact of management information systems (MIS) on quality assurance (QA): A case study in Jordan. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 4(2), 93-110.

Masa'deh, R. (2016). The role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing job satisfaction at Aqaba five star hotels in Jordan. *Communications and Network*, 8(4), 219.

Masa'deh, R., Obeidat, B., Zyod, D., & Gharaibeh, A. (2015). The associations among transformational leadership, transactional leadership, knowledge sharing, job performance, and firm performance: A theoretical model. *Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)*, 4(2), 848-866.

Obeidat, B., Tarhini, A., & Aqqad, N. (2017). The impact of intellectual capital on innovation via the mediating role of knowledge management: A structural equation modelling approach. *International Journal of Knowledge Management Studies*, 8(3-4), 273-298.

Oliver, C. (1997). Sustainable competitive advantage: Combining institutional and resource based views. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18, 697-713.

Oreg, S. (2006). Personality, context, and resistance to organizational change. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 15(1), 73-101.

Pardo-del-Val, M., Martinez-Fuentes, C., & Roig-Dobón, S. (2012). Participative management and its influence on organizational change. *Management Decision*, 50(10), 1843-1860.

Parvin, M.M. & Kabir, M.N. (2011). Factors affecting employee job satisfaction of pharmaceutical companies. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(9), 113.

Petrou, P., Demerouti, E., & Xanthopoulou, D. (2017). Regular versus cutback-related change: The role of employee job crafting in organizational change contexts of different nature. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 24(1), 62.

Petrou, P., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W.B. (2018). Crafting the change: The role of employee job crafting behaviors for successful organizational change. *Journal of Management*, 44(5), 1766-1792.

Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach* (7th ed). United Kingdom: John Wiley and Sons Ltd.

Sarraf, A.R. (2018). Relationship between emotional labor and intrinsic job satisfaction: The moderating role of gender. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Organization Management*, 7(227), 2.

Schermerhorn Jr, J.R., Osborn, R.N., Uhl-Bien, M., & Hunt, J.G. (2012). *Organizational behavior* 12th ed discussion 2 things Ohio University. Wayne State University, University of Nebraska, Texas Tech University.

Schneider, B., Brief, A.P., & Guzzo, R.A. (1996). Creating a climate and culture for sustainable organizational change. *Organizational Dynamics*, 24(4), 7-19.

Schouteten, R.L., & Vleuten, T. (2013). *Organizational change and job satisfaction among voluntary and paid workers in a Dutch voluntary organization*. (pp. 1-33). The Netherlands: Radboud University.

Seo, M.G., Taylor, M.S., Hill, N.S., Zhang, X., Tesluk, P.E., & Lorinkova, N.M. (2012). The role of affect and leadership during organizational change. *Personnel Psychology*, 65(1), 121-165.

Shah, N., Irani, Z., & Sharif, A.M. (2017). Big data in an HR context: Exploring organizational change readiness, employee attitudes and behaviors. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, 366-378.

The relationship between organizational changes and job satisfaction in ...

Shin, J., Taylor, M.S., & Seo, M.G. (2012). Resources for change: The relationships of organizational inducements and psychological resilience to employees' attitudes and behaviors toward organizational change. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55(3), 727-748.

Spector, P.E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences* (Vol. 3). Sage Publications.

Suifan, T., Diab, H., & Abdallah, A. (2017). Does organizational justice affect turnover-intention in a developing country? The mediating role of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *Journal of Management Development*, 36(9), 1137-1148.

Tarcan, M., Hikmet, N., Schooley, B. Top, M., & Tarcan, G.Y. (2017). An analysis of the relationship between burnout, socio-demographic and workplace factors and job satisfaction among emergency department health professionals. *Applied Nursing Research*, 34, 40-47.

Tierney, P. (1999). Work relations as a precursor to a psychological climate for change: The role of work group supervisors and peers. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 12, 120-133.

Thirumalai, C., Chandhini, S.A., & Vaishnavi, M. (2017). Analysing the concrete compressive strength using Pearson and Spearman. *International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology, ICECA*, 2, 215-218.

Tsounis, A., & Sarafis, P. (2018). Validity and reliability of the Greek translation of the job satisfaction survey (JSS). *BMC Psychology*, 6(1), 27.

Van den Heuvel, M., Demerouti, E., Bakker, A.B., & Schaufeli, W.B. (2010). Personal resources and work engagement in the face of change. *Contemporary Occupational Health Psychology: Global Perspectives on Research and Practice*, 1, 124-150.

Von Treuer, K., Karantzas, G., McCabe, M., Mellor, D., Konis, A., Davison, T.E., & O'Connor, D. (2018). Organizational factors associated with readiness for change in residential aged care settings. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1), 77.

Wanberg, C.R., & Banas, J.T. (2000). Predictors and outcomes of openness to changes in a reorganizing workplace. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85, 132-142.

Weil, D. (2018). Creating a strategic enforcement approach to address wage theft: One academic's journey in organizational change. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 60(3), 437-460.

Yousef, D.A. (2000). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction as predictors of attitudes toward organizational change in a non-western setting. *Personnel Review*, 29(5), 567-592.

Yousef, D.A. (2017). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction and attitudes toward organizational change: a study in the local government. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 40(1), 77-88.